

MATERIALS FOR TEACHING CULTURE: LITERATURE AND NEWSPAPER.**Gavharoy Botirova****Andijan State Institute for Foreign Languages,
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Abstract: Culture is a factor, which is an essential aspect in language teaching and learning. Despite the complexity of defining the concept, students can be made aware of culture through a variety of teaching materials. This paper reviews literature as a tool to teach cultural awareness in the EFL classroom. Using literature in the classroom and offering students the opportunity to encounter different cultures in the Swedish curriculum (Skolverket, 2011). Given the particular importance of the relation between literature and culture, two aspects have been looked into in this review. Firstly, what genres of literature have been mostly used and are typically preferred among students? And secondly, how has teaching cultural awareness through literature been approached and what sorts of teaching strategies and methods have been applied? The findings show that literature and culture have a complicated but intertwined connection and literature is a beneficial tool that should be used for several reasons, especially for developing students' cultural awareness. This review will be concluded by a discussion and possible topics for future research.

Key words: culture, literature, newspaper, media, TV, society article, fiction, materials, cultural understanding.

Introduction

The media provides an excellent source for discovering a “new” place and making our students more culturally competent. The press, TV news broadcasts, and talk shows can provide the linguistic and cultural authenticity that our students need in order to become culturally competent. These authentic texts provide valuable opportunities for students to gain insights into the target culture. Facts in newspapers or in TV news broadcasts are “food for thought”, which can be used to help students generate cultural hypotheses. Culture is not seen as homogenous or static. Since newspapers have a wide spectrum of social or ethnic class, gender, age, occupation etc., they may be regarded as a significant tool for evaluating values, perspectives and understanding of the people living in a foreign country. Besides, newspapers cover current issues which help learners to get an accurate idea about target culture. When learning a new language, whether it is as a second or foreign language, this usually includes a cultural component (Byram, 2014; Kramsch, 2006; Risager, 2012). This has been the norm for language teaching for a long time, and most teachers will tell you that this is an important part of the subject (Byram, 2013). In the English subject curriculum, this is expressed both in the Purpose section, where it is stated that “the subject of English shall contribute to providing insight into the way people live and different cultures where English is the primary or the official language” and by the fact that one of the main subject areas is called “Culture, Society and literature”, which “focuses on cultural understanding in a broad sense” (NMER, 2006, 2013). Although culture has been a part of language teaching for a long time, its position has change over time. Lund (2014, p. 177) sums up the reasons for why culture has been and still is emphasized in language learning in four points. The first is related to the motivation of the learner, as learning about the country where the target language is

used and its speakers might be a motivating factor for the learners. The second point has to do with language learning and communicative abilities; cultural knowledge help the students communicate better and get references in the target language. The third point is developing the students' general knowledge, as learning about cultural topics in the English subject will contribute to the cognitive development and general knowledge level of the students. Finally, the last point is intercultural competence; gaining insight and knowledge about other cultures as well as our own will help communication with people from different cultural backgrounds (Lund, 2014). In the following sections, the role of some materials in teaching culture in language teaching will be presented.

The usage of literature has many benefits in the classroom, which Fenner (2001) discusses. She starts by mentioning the authenticity of literary texts, which is about the intent of fulfilling a purpose within the language community where it was created, which Liddicoat and Scarino (2013) also agrees on. Secondly, literature offers the learners sufficient of opportunity to discover and explore the diversity of language but also culture. It creates room for the student's own personal interpretation and opinion. Additionally, through the foreign cultures in the literatures, students' can receive an important and necessary perspective of not only other cultures but also their own culture and an outside perspective of themselves. Fenner (2001) also argues that literature does not only represent cultures that are present today since it also offers students a chance of exploring and receiving an insight and representation of cultures of the past as well. Lastly, she discusses another important aspect that concerns identification and self-awareness, since through literature we increase an indirect understanding of the world. When a text is reflected upon the reader might turn the interpretations upon themselves, which subsequently can result in enriched understanding and self-awareness.

Just as the concept of culture, literature can be difficult to define. Encyclopaedia Britannica (2017) defines literature as a body of written works and it can be divided into a variety of different categories such as language, national origin, historical period, genre and subject matter. Moreover, it is mentioned that "literature is a form of human expression", but not all written words can be considered as literature. Depending on whom the question is asked, the answers to what literature includes can vary. However, the common division can often be fiction and non-fiction literature. Fiction is a quite popular type of literature used in the language-teaching classroom. Fiction is also emphasized in the curriculum for Swedish upper secondary school (2011) under central content "form and content in different types of fiction" (p. 54). Literature contains a variety of genres and Reyes-Torres (2011) states that for example detective fiction is a genre that can be an effective tool, the mystery, suspense and action in the stories can appeal to the students. The genre can be an approach to provoke discussions and be used as a pedagogical implement in the classroom to explore different issues relating cultural Interaction, historical and political moments from all over the world. Erkaya (2005) puts attention on the benefits of using short stories in the classroom and mentions that short stories can be motivational and lead to cultural and higher order thinking. Since short stories often have a beginning, middle and an end it can encourage students to continue reading and finish it to find out how the conflict is being resolved. Youth literature and the classics are two very popular genres often used in the classroom. Youth literature can be especially beneficial since the themes, settings, situations and characters may have a close

connection and can be relatable to the students (Tseng, 2010). The classics can help us understand the past, the changes that have occurred over time and hopefully work as a tool to prevent us from repeating those mistakes.

Seelye (1993) maintains that the mass media is a good source for current data. It offers real interaction with the target language and culture, and is a valuable instructional resource. They are superior to the simplified language in edited texts, and contribute to the learning of coping skills. Newspapers also offer “snapshots” of the segments of the target culture, making them a logical medium. Teachers must be aware that newspapers and magazines are commercial enterprises aimed at a particular target readership; and as such they may reflect the values, interests and biases of the readership; as well as those of the owners, editorial staff, and the political milieu. Understanding audience needs helps producers decide on the content and delivery of messages (Blatchford, 86). Writing articles for newspapers and magazines also requires a sense of who the readers will be. For example, the headlines and first paragraph of a news article have to contain information about the what, when, where, who, and how of an event to provide the gist of a story for busy readers. Newspapers can be a valuable tool for promoting critical thinking skills, enhancing students’ writing and reading skills, and developing their vocabulary knowledge. Newspapers can help students to think along various dimensions, and thus gain control over media texts instead of simply accepting them superficially. They can also open doors to various disciplines, e.g. cultural studies and media studies, which can bring diversity into language classrooms. An important point to keep in mind, however, is that newspapers should be viewed as subject matter in their own right, and be used with a principled approach aiming at improving students’ abilities not just in language but also in critical and creative thinking, and their attitudes to target culture.

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